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THE EFFECTS OF Mg CONTENTS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE AC8A ALLOY REINFORCED WITH ASZ SHORT FIBERS

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SUMMARY : The effect of interfacial reaction on the mechanical properties of the AC8A Al alloy reinforced with ASZ short fibers(hereinafter ASZ/AC8A composite) was studied. In the ASZ/AC8A composite, the interfacial reaction was observed to proceed between the SiO₂ binder layer and Mg of the matrix to form MgAl₂O₄ at the interface. Formation of MgAl₂O₄ was believed to enhance the interfacial bonding strength resulting in the improved composite strength. However, the interfacial reaction in the ASZ/AC8A composite always took place at the expense of Mg in the matrix, resulting in the composite devoid of the Mg bearing precipitates such as Al₂CuMg and Mg₂Si. Interfacial reaction mechanisms were investigated for composites containing various amounts of Mg contents. The resultant mechanical properties of the composite were measured to determine the adequate amount of Mg contents within the composite. Microstructural changes of the composite were observed using TEM and DSC to provide qualitative analyses on the experimental observations.

KEYWORDS : Interfacial reaction, Phase equilibrium, Mechanical properties

1. INTRODUCTION

MMCs not only present improved mechanical properties, but also possess other material properties, such as low thermal expansion coefficient and high temperature strength etc [1-3] suitable for automotive applications. The use of MMCs for automotive pistons has been studied as a means for a cost-effective solution for severe operating conditions [4-6]. Another advantage of the composite pistons is the design freedom with which the hazardous emission, such as HC, NOx etc., can be reduced. Considering that ~70 % of the hazardous emission originates from the crevice volume between the liner and the piston, moving the top ring position toward the top land of the piston can reduce the crevice volume, thereby reduce the hazardous emission. This, however, can weaken the strength of the ring groove region, therefore may result in the failure of the piston during service [7,8].

In general, MMC components are normally produced using squeeze casting and heat treated before machining. During heat treatment, the interfacial reactions between the fiber and

the matrix take place in most short fiber reinforced Al alloy composites. Such interfacial reactions can alter the chemical composition of the matrix, the loss of Mg in particular [9] and, therefore, the material properties of the composites can vary during the heat treatment [10,11]. In the present study, the interfacial reactions between the ceramic fiber and the matrix were studied. The effect of Mg contents within the matrix on the interfacial reactions was analyzed based on theory and experiments. The effect of the interfacial reaction on the mechanical properties of the composites was also evaluated.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Preform preparation

Fibers used in this study are termed ASZ fibers having composition of Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , and ZrO_2 in 3:5:2 ratio and are amorphous in their as-fabricated state. Fibers less than $150\mu\text{m}$ in length were collected and mixed with binders(organic 0.1%, inorganic SiO_2 3%) in a slurry dispersion. Approximately 1 vol. % of glucose was added into the solution as a dispersant. The solution was then ultrasonicated for 5 minutes to break up the fiber clusters. After agitation, the solution was fed into the mold followed by removing water using a vacuum extraction method. Preforms with dimensions of $80\times 110\times 20\text{mm}$ and the fiber volume fraction of 11% were prepared. The wet preforms are dried and subsequently heated at an appropriate temperature to remove the organic binders. The fibers in the preform were aligned in a two dimensional random planar orientation, with planes parallel to the top and bottom surfaces of the rectangular shaped preform.

2.2 Composite fabrication

The preforms were sintered at 1100°C for 2 hours to make the preforms strong enough to resist the pressure exerted by the molten metal during squeeze casting. The matrix used was the AC8A Al alloy, an Al-Si alloy with the eutectic composition commonly used for pistons. The actual chemical composition of the matrix was Al-12.7Si-1.1Cu-0.9Mg (in wt.%). The Al alloy melted at 670°C was infiltrated into the preform using a casting pressure of 100MPa. The squeeze cast composites were T6 treated(510°C for 3.5hrs, water quenching, 230°C for 3.5 hrs, air cooling). Round bar tensile test specimens with their tensile direction parallel to the fibers long axis were made from the T6 treated and the as-cast composites. Tensile tests were carried out using a constant cross-head speed of 2mm/min. To evaluate the effect of Mg contents on the hardness and the strength of the composites, composites using Al-12.7Si-1.1Cu-xM alloys with various Mg contents were also prepared.

2.3 Microstructural observation

Observation of detailed 3-dimensional morphologies of the interfacial reaction products, which, in general, is not feasible under TEM, was carried out using SEM. To prepare specimens, fibers as well as the reaction products were extracted from the composite using an electrochemical dissolution method. The electrolyte used for the extraction process was 20 vol.% HNO_3 in

distilled water. The voltage and current used for the extraction were 11 volts DC and 6 amp, respectively. The electrolyte was maintained at $\sim 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the extraction procedure. The extracted fibers were coated with 80 \AA thick Pt to help observe the interfacial reaction products at high magnifications using Hitachi S-4200 Field Emission scanning electron microscope operated at 15 kV.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of the ASZ/AC8A composite

Microstructures of the fibers : Prior to squeeze casting, preforms were sintered to make preforms possess the strength required to resist the pressure of infiltrating molten metal. During sintering, partial melting of the SiO_2 binder takes place, enhancing the strength of the preform by binding fibers together. Although the compressive strength of the preform itself increased with increasing sintering temperature, no further increase in the strength of the composite was observed when the preform is sintered at temperatures above 1200°C . The effect of preform sintering temperatures on the mechanical properties of the ASZ/AC8A composites was reported elsewhere [12], therefore will not be dealt in detail in this study.

In the earlier study, we have reported that the best properties, such as wear resistance, tensile strength, etc. could be obtained when the preform is sintered at temperatures in the range of $1100\text{-}1200^{\circ}\text{C}$ [12]. At this temperature range, partial melting of the SiO_2 binder takes place. Shown in Fig.1 is the XRD recorded from the raw(as-fabricated) fibers and fibers sintered at 1100°C for 2hrs, showing the presence of crystallized ZrO_2 and mullite($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$). The fibers sintered at 1100°C were also observed using TEM. As can be seen from the beam centered dark field image in Fig.2(a), nano-sized ZrO_2 and mullite were observed clearly, while SiO_2 remained as the amorphous phase.

Fig.1 XRD patterns recorded from the as-fabricated fibers and the fibers sintered at 1100°C for 2hrs, showing crystallization of fibers due to sintering.

Microstructures of the matrix : Fig.2(c) is the TEM dark field image and corresponding SAD patterns recorded from the [100] zone axis of the matrix, showing the presence of platelet θ -phase(CuAl_2) precipitated on the (100) planes of the matrix. Although the matrix contains ~1% of Mg, Mg bearing precipitates, such as S-phase(Al_2CuMg), were not observed. Considering that S-phase is a typical precipitate that can be observed from the Al-Si-Cu-Mg system, one may ask a question why precipitates associated with Mg are not observed. The later part of this paper deals with the interfacial reaction to provide an answer for the above experimental observation.

Fig.2(a) A TEM dark field image of the ASZ fibers sintered at 1100°C for 2hrs, (b) the SAD pattern corresponding to Fig.2(a), and (c) A TEM dark field image recorded from the [001] zone of the aluminum, showing the presence of the θ -phase in the matrix

Microstructure of the interface : Fig.3(a) is the SEM micrograph, showing the presence of the interfacial reaction products formed on the surface of the fibers and clusters of the binder located between the two adjacent fibers. The reaction products were identified as MgAl_2O_4 formed as a result of the reaction between the SiO_2 binder and the matrix during the solution treatment. When observed at higher magnifications, the morphologies of MgAl_2O_4 crystals were either octahedral or truncated triangle as seen in Fig.3(b). Detailed explanations on the phase identification and reaction mechanism at the interface are analyzed on the proceeding section.

Fig.3(a) A SEM micrograph showing the presence of $MgAl_2O_4$ crystals which were formed as a result of the interfacial reaction between the binder and the matrix alloy. Arrows indicated in the micrograph denote the hair cracks formed on the binder during drying process. (b) A magnified view of Fig.3(a) showing detailed morphologies of $MgAl_2O_4$ crystals.

Fig.4(a) is the TEM bright field image recorded from the interfacial region of the ASZ/AC8A composite, showing a dark contrast at the subsurface region of the fiber. Since the contrast difference in TEM can be raised by the difference in the solute concentration, analytical measurements of the solute concentration, Mg in particular, were carried out at regions in the vicinity of the interface using EDS. Fig.4(b) is the variation in the Mg contents measured along a direction perpendicular to the interface, showing that the penetration of Mg into the fiber took place. However, in the present study, detailed reaction mechanism on how the diffused Mg reacted with the fiber could not be analyzed.

Fig.4(a) A TEM bright field image showing the presence of the contrast band at the subsurface of the fiber (b) EDS analysis result showing Mg penetration into the fiber skin.

3.2 Interfacial reactions in the ASZ/AC8A composite

Model formulation : The composite system, i.e., ASZ/AC8A composite having thin SiO_2 layers

on fibers, was considered for calculations. Thin SiO₂ binder layers enveloping ASZ fibers in Al alloy matrices tend to transform into more stable oxides by reacting with Al and Mg dissolved in the matrices. This is because, from the point of view of thermodynamics, oxygen affinities of Al and Mg are high enough to reduce SiO₂ layers [13].

In order to evaluate the interfacial reaction between SiO₂ and Al/Mg, the following three interfacial reactions to form oxides as reaction products were considered.

where all the compounds Al₂O₃, MgAl₂O₄, MgO and free Si are in solid state and Al and Mg are in dissolved state, i.e. in the α-Al and liquid matrices. The above three reactions are spontaneous, since the Gibbs energies of Al₂O₃, MgAl₂O₄ and MgO are much lower than that of SiO₂ and the interface is free from Si at the initial stage of the reactions. Therefore, the above three reactions would compete one another.

Considering that Mg has higher oxygen affinity than Al, the reaction product might be gradually changed from Al₂O₃ to either MgAl₂O₄ or MgO depending on process temperatures and Mg content in an Al alloy. To evaluate the phase equilibria among Al₂O₃, MgAl₂O₄, and MgO, Eqs.(4) and (5) were obtained by manipulating Eqs. (1)-(3).

The reaction directions of Eqs.(4) and (5) depend on the Gibbs energy changes associated with the reactions assuming the presence of local thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface.

Analyses of the calculated results : The stable interfacial reaction products within the ASZ/AC8A composite are predicted by evaluating Eqs.(4) and (5). All thermodynamic calculations in the present work have been carried out using a computer software Thermo-Calc developed by Sundman et al [14] and detailed procedures for calculations can be found elsewhere [15].

Phase equilibria calculated for the ASZ/AC8A composite are shown graphically in Fig.6. The theoretical calculations were also verified by experiments and the results are superposed on the same graph. As can be seen from the graphs, when composite systems containing low Mg contents are exposed at high temperatures, the formation of MgAl₂O₄ according to the reaction (1) is favored. On the other hand, composite systems containing high Mg contents tend to form MgO even at low temperatures according to the reaction (2).

Fig.5 Interfacial reaction calculated as a function of heat treatment temperatures and the Mg contents in the ASZ/AC8A composite superimposed on the experimental data.

3.3 Effect of Mg contents on the material properties

Most preforms used to produce short fibers reinforced composites use inorganic SiO_2 as a binding medium. Such SiO_2 binders will be engaged in the interfacial reactions during the heat treatment, resulting in consumption of a certain amount of Mg within the matrix as a result of the interfacial reaction. The amount of Mg consumed due to the interfacial reaction is directionally proportional to the amount of SiO_2 used to fabricate the preforms. Approximate amount of Mg can be calculated under reasonable assumptions, i.e., 1) the density of SiO_2 being 2.0g/cm^3 and 2) all SiO_2 binders are to be involved in the interfacial reaction to form MgAl_2O_4 . Simple calculations to predict the amount of Mg consumed due to the interfacial reaction were carried out based on Eq.1. The calculated result is shown in Eq.(6). As seen in this equation, the amount of the Mg exhaustion increases linearly with increasing amount of the binder.

$$Mg(\text{ wt. \%}) = \frac{55V}{274 - 1.04V} \quad (6)$$

where V is the volume fraction of the SiO_2 binder used to fabricate preforms.

The preform used in this study contains ~ 3 wt.% of SiO_2 as a binder. Assuming that all of these binding aids are transformed into MgAl_2O_4 , approximately ~ 0.6 wt.% of Mg can be consumed. In addition, as already discussed in Fig.4, Mg was observed to diffuse into the subsurface of the fibers. Based on EDS analyses in Fig.4(b), amount of Mg penetrated into the fibers was approximated to be ~ 0.3 wt.%. Therefore, most of Mg within the matrix (~ 1.0 wt.%) could be consumed as a result of the interfacial reaction. Such a hypothesis can be the reason why Mg bearing precipitates within the matrix were not observed from TEM.

Considering that Mg bearing precipitates such as Al_2CuMg act as a major source for strengthening the matrix, adding adequate amounts of Mg within the matrix can enhance the strength of the composite. To experimentally determine the adequate amounts of Mg that have to be added into the matrix, 0-3.6 wt.% of Mg were added into the ternary Al-12.7Si-1.1Cu alloy to prepare composites and matrices, i.e., Al-12.7Si-1.1Cu-xMg alloys. Composites with various Mg contents were produced using squeeze casting.

Fig.6(a) presents the variations in the hardness of the composites and the matrices measured as a function of Mg contents. A substantial increase in the hardness was observed from both the composites and the matrices by adding a small amount of Mg. However, with increasing Mg addition, the hardness was observed to converge to constant values.

Fig.6(a) Variations in the hardness of the composite and the matrix alloy measured as a function of Mg contents. (b) Variation in the hardness difference between the composites and the matrix alloys measured as a function of Mg contents.

Fig.6(a) presents the variations in the difference in the hardness obtained by subtracting the hardness of the matrices from those of the composites in Fig.6(a). The trend obtained can be divided into 4 different regions as indicated in the graph. First of all, as can be seen from region A, the hardness of the composite is higher than that of the matrix even in the absence of Mg. At region B, the hardness difference between the composite and the matrix was observed to increase significantly even when a very small amount of Mg up to 0.5% was added into the matrix. At region C, i.e., 0.5-1.0% of Mg, almost no additional change in the hardness difference was observed. At region D, the hardness difference was observed to increase gradually and eventually no further increase in the hardness was observed beyond ~2% of Mg. Therefore, the composite sample, i.e., ASZ/(AC8A+1.3%Mg) composite was fabricated by adding additional 1.3 wt.% of Mg into the AC8A matrix.

Fig.7 is the beam centered TEM dark field image and corresponding SAD patterns

recorded from the [100] zone axis of the matrix, showing the presence of the rod shaped S-phase as well as the platelet θ -phases (CuAl_2) in the ASZ/(AC8A+1.3%Mg) composite. Tensile tests were carried out on the ASZ/(AC8A+1.3%Mg) composite to evaluate the tensile properties of the newly-made composite. Shown in Fig.8 are the stress-strain curves obtained from the ASZ/AC8A composite and the ASZ/(AC8A+1.3%Mg) composite, showing that the yield strength was increased by 16% (36MPa) compared to the old one. Such an increase in the yield strength is considered to be due to the formation of the S-phase in the matrix.

Fig.7 A TEM dark field image and the corresponding SAD pattern recorded from the [001] zone of the Al of the ASZ/(AC8A+1.3%Mg) composite, showing the presence of the S-phase as well as the θ -phase.

Fig.8 Engineering stress-strain curves showing the enhanced strength of the composite by adding the additional Mg.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on studies on interfacial reactions in the ASZ/AC8A composites, following conclusions could be drawn.

1. Methodology to predict and control the interfacial reactions in the short fiber reinforced Al

alloy composites was demonstrated. The interfacial reactions in the ASZ/AC8A composite were dependent on the heat treating temperatures and the matrix composition, Mg contents in particular. When composite systems with low Mg contents are exposed at high temperatures, the formation of MgAl_2O_4 is favored. On the other hand, composite systems with high Mg contents tend to form MgO even at high temperatures.

2. In the case of the 11 vol.% ASZ/AC8A composite, approximately 0.6-0.9 wt.% of Mg can be consumed due to the reaction between SiO_2 and Mg in the matrix. As a result, the composite strength could be reduced.
3. Adding additional Mg into the AC8A matrix was observed to enhance the strength of the composite. Such an experimental result is considered to be due to formation of the S-phase within the matrix.

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